

HISTORICAL ISSUES IN THE EPOS OF “BOOK OF DEDE KORKUT”*

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the historical problems of the epic Book of Dede Korkut, which occupy an important place in the heroic epics associated with the early middle Ages. As the researcher of the epic Book of Dede Korkut notes, this fact raises interest in comparing the events of the characters of the epic with real history. According to the general decisions of researchers, who study the epic Book of Dede Korkut, most of the events described in the epic, reflect the historical reality. In order to investigate the main problem, the question of the author, in which it is written, in any historical situation or in any historical period.

Key words: Book of Dede Korkut, Azerbaijan, historic character, military democracy, Z.M. Bunyadov, Y. Mahmudov, V. Minorsky, F. Sumer

Introduction

The epos of Book of Dede Korkut, which occupies a special place among folk heroic epos of the early Middle Ages of world people, is characterized as a heroic epos. This fact perceived by the researchers unambiguously, greatly increases the interest to compare the events related to the activity of epic personages with the real history.

According to the unanimous scientific findings of the prominent researchers of “Book of Dede Korkut”, Azerbaijan was the place where epos describes events, as well as the epos itself. One of the first researchers of Book of Dede Korkut, V.V. Bartold noted that geographical names, political situation and cultural environment showed the last formation place of Oghuz epic was the historical place territory of Caucasus. [1, p. 115-116].

The geographical names reflected in the epos, not considering in the south Syria, in the west Rumen (Byzantium), are almost belong to the South Caucasus, especially to Azerbaijan. The epos of “Book of Dede Korkut” associated with Azerbaijan with all its geographical and socio-ethnic features have been incorporated by people singer (ashig) who lived within the Azerbaijani people [2, p. 22].

The place of the events described in the epos is shown as the territory of Azerbaijan and Armenia [3, p.121]. In addition, Jirmunski also claims the events of the some parts of the epos with related to the reality of the Central Asian oghuzs. An author, who paid wide attention to the researching of epos, compare the part of “Bamsy Beirak” of epos with the epos “Alpamish” [4, p. 9].

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According to the general opinion of the researchers of Book of Dede Korkut, many of the epos reflected in the epic reflects the historical reality, but the constant change of the last copy that we have made has led to a number of contradictions.

For the researching of the problem, it is more important to clarify the issues of epic in which historical situation and which historical period was written.

Traditions of South Caucasus Oghuz turks, religious beliefs up to Islamic period, the names of different heroes, the main directions of social structure which are displayed in the epos gives us to concern it not only to 11th century, but also more older periods.

The researchers put forward different versions about the formation and written period of epos. In the comment written by F.Zeynalov and S.Alizade to the most important publication of Book of Dede Korkut published in the 80s of 20th century it showed that religious views of Oghuz turks concerns to the 3-4 centuries [5, p. 16].

As for events displayed in the epos, the authors consider the most period of events took place to the VI-VIII centuries. However, some researchers do not exclude that some parts of the epos were added later [5, p.17]. It is also noted that the epos was formed in the VI-VIII centuries, complete formation in VII-IX centuries, and written not later than X century [5, p.17].

A.Yakuboski also noted that this epos is more important source to learn not only XV and XVI century, but also ancient periods [3, p. 16, 24].

As mentioned above, V.Jirmunski is one of the authors who told original scientific thoughts about Book of Dede Korkut. The author noted the period of the formation of the parts of the epos to IX-X centuries, but they were polished on the literary again in the XV century [1, p. 140]. V.Jirmunski also noted some parts of epos, especially the part of Deli Domrul belong to the V-VI centuries [1, p. 141].

The first publisher and the most prominent researcher of Book of Dede Korkut in Azerbaijan Hamid Arasli showed to be written of epos in the XI XII centuries in the introduction of the epic which was published in 1962.

Researching on the language of epos, the prominent linguist scientist A.Damirchizadeh considered Book of Dede Korkut is belong to Azerbaijani monument, and also showed it to be written later VIII-IX centuries [6].

The prominent researcher Xalig Koroghlu in his researching connected to Book of Dede Korkut expressed his interesting views formation place and history of epos. The author came to a conclusion that this epos was created from ancient times, and ended its formation in the territory of Azerbaijan in the XI-XIII centuries in his work called "Tukmen literature". The researcher considers the "Oghuz tribes" of Book of Dede Korkut were local people of Azerbaijan who were on bad terms with neighbors.

Scientific researches of last period prove these conceptions of the author. Since the second half of the last century, views about the territory of Azerbaijan were still the object of the settlement of the Turks tribes before XI centuries, and the considerations of the Turkish communities to be able to influence the ethno demographic situation of the population here were put forward and scientifically substantiated.

Academician ZMBunyadov played a great role in this sphere. The author considering wrong the thoughts of V.Minorsky and F.Sumer connected to the turkization of Azerbaijan's territory in the XI-XII centuries, write: "This conception who consider that Turks came to the territory of Azerbaijan from other territory is wrong, because then local and the existence of turks tribes was ignored"[7, p. 198.]

It is noted that this conception of the author was approved by early middle ages sources. And also this idea was affirmed by Y. Mahmudov. He notes that Azerbaijan's territory is a content of all-turks world [8, p. 52].

The author, who considers Azerbaijan as one of the regions where the Turkish ethnos has become a unified nation, shows that as a result of this process, the general Turkish language has also been formed and the most important indicator of this is the epos of "Book of Dede Korkut" [8, p.28].

The facts mentioned above from different authors, Book of Dede Korkut belongs to Oghuz Turks.

"Kitabi Dede Korkut" is not only the primary and masterpiece of Azerbaijani literature and is also the main source of Azerbaijani history [9, p.82].

Once more the above mentioned findings reinforce the idea that the monument belongs to Azerbaijani people and turns this epos to irreplaceable source about Azerbaijan's history. It is no coincidence that researcher Y.Mahmudov treats Book of Dede Korkut as a historical source and emphasizes its importance in this direction [10].

In some cases it is difficult to name heroic epos as a historical or legend. The historical background of heroic epos is controversial, and this is due to the fact that it violates the accustomed rules. Some

researchers have speculated that they were special, and later that it had been transformed into a generalized epoch, while the others understood that the epos never tried to be a date. [11]

The events described in Book of Dede Korkut and the many participants of these events are compared with the "true" historical chronology of Abulgazi Khan Bahadir's "Turkmen Genius", as well as by Fazlullah Rashidaddin's Jame-et-Tevarih's relevant events and characters. [9, p. 86].

Although it is no exception to use the book of Dede Korkut epos as a historical source, being of paradox with the historical scientific understanding of the concept coming from the epic character of the work slightly complicates the issue.

The world of heroic epos is far away from the past as it is not the usual past, which is not exposed to quality changes, and is not placed on the line of time. Connection with this problem, a prominent researcher, M.Baxtin, says: "Epic past called absolute past, at the same time and precious past, is a gradual, purely time-lapse of reality."

Taking into consideration all of these, as well as the historical epoch of the epos, it is possible to define the period in which the events reflected in the epos reflect the exact period of reality.

The problem, which reflects the thoughts of the sequence of historical events enclosed certain period of Azerbaijan's history, demand to epos to be used as a historical source.

Taking the critical approach to the historical source, it is important to touch upon the specific historical conditions in which the epic is created, as well as the author or authors of the epos. It should be noted that critical approach to the text of Book of Dede Korkut epos from point of view of historically-philologically gives us to express our view about the parts of the unit in the epos.

VVBartold, who for the first time in 1893 expressed his views on the unity of the epos, also denied his opinion later, and concluded that the poetic values of the rich were not the same, and that even the rich would be called an "oguzname" Separately. All these proves that the epos occurred in different historical periods. We believe that the real events took place in different periods of our history, been reflected in various parts of the epos.

In general, based on the achievements in the field of history and philology, it is possible to say that the leading and almost major themes of the epic go deep in our history - the period of "military democracy", the collapse of the primitive community. At the same time, it should be noted that the text of the epic has undergone wear and dictation for many centuries has changed the real picture of those events. Some of the authors say that some of the events mentioned in Book of Dede Korkut were written in the 6th-7th centuries. The reason for this comment is the name of the 14th century historian Abubakr Abdullah ibn Aybek Dawadari called "Oguzname". It has been shown that Oghuzname was translated into Persian and then into Arabic [12, p. 282]. It is interesting that Devadari gives information about the story of Tepegöz from Oguznama, which he sees in Arabic, which is almost the same story in Dede Korkut.

The well-known Azerbaijani literary scholar, Amin Abid Dawadari, has come to the conclusion that the Turkish text of the Oguznama was written down in the V-VI centuries [12, p.48-52].

Along with all epic heritages, "Book of Dede Korkut", which is a historical episode of the history of the Azerbaijani history, reflects the relationship of the Turks with their neighbors, especially the glorious war history against the enemy forces and their patrons.

This approach to Book of Dede Korkut is crucial for identifying specific enemies who look at our lands and combining the information in epos with synchronized written sources.

It is possible to conclude that the historical information that was delivered to us in the epos mentioned above is not one but the different periods of time that are not close to one another. Information covering each of these periods was disproportionately distributed in the epos. In other words, "the Oguznama ridge, which reflects the activity of the oggs in the history square in the form of epos and sources, is a periodical reading of this or that language in some other languages" [13, p.89] .

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